

Institution of Family in Literature, Culture & Society

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19311325

Abstract:

Human Development Programme highlights that there is still no society where women were fare as well as men. Women have been fighting to free their half of the total population of the world from male oppression. Women were engaged in the various movements and struggles which revolutions their lives. Woman is primarily characterized by the spirit of rebelliousness. This spirit is manifested through diverse means and modes. A woman's rejection of her assigned role inside the family and society, refusal to follow the traditional paths, inherent revulsion to the idealism associated with normal physical functions of the body such as menstruation, pregnancy and childbirth or procreation. In a society where young people choosing their partners is considered scandalizing, pre-marital affairs are not looked at approvingly, though they are not a rarity anymore. Thus, both men and women operate within strict parameters of social codes and taboos. Woman feels lonely in the face of vast external world. Her loneliness is intensified when she feels the sense of belonging nowhere. Different regions of India where is religious, cultural and social ethos and despite the religious, cultural and social backgrounds there runs a common thread that serves to bind them together. This common thread is the predicament of the women with a certain point of view.

Keywords: Male Oppression, Parameters, Social Ethos.

Introduction:

Women became very much confident as well as motivate because of liberty. There was a confidence in the mind of woman for their future life. Women had the freedom to choose their life partners and they also had access to education. Women also enjoyed a certain amount of economic independence as they used to engage in spinning and weaving activities at home. Some women used to help in farming activities also. It is true that literature takes particular notion to the extreme point where everything looks realistic. And to make this literature entertaining the writer always tries their level best to make the realistic into unrealistic and the unrealistic into realistic. The colonial rulers were sympathetic towards the suffering and oppression of Indian women. When

we think of the novel as the form of Literature, we refer to the literature of the masses which finds favor with large number of people. Some modern critics believe that the novelists of the past have paid too much attention to the story or plot and too little to psychology. Against this there has grown up something called as the anti-novel. Somerset Maugham says that the anti – novelist tells the story for its own sake as a debased form of fiction. It seems the stories are deeply rooted in the human animal as the sense of property. Firstly, men used to gather round the camp-fire or in the market place to listen to the story. So, the desire of story-telling is very strong among the people. For most people the telling of a story remains the important thing in a novel, just as it was in the novella of Boccaccio's time,

the romances of the Middle Ages, and the prose fictions of classical times. However, the most modern novels differ from these more or less distant forbearers in a number of ways. Literature has a sociological background of class and community distinctions.

The present study is the investigation of woman's status in the selected novels of Maitreyi Pushpa's *Alma Kabutari*. Maitreyi Pushpa received liveliness and energy by the cultures and languages of Bundeli and Brij. She is the only woman writer in Hindi who has chosen to write about rural India. Her writing is a constant struggle against the feudal system which still prevails in Indian villages. Her protagonists are always fearless women upholding feminine dignity, who suffer and resist the male domination. No other woman writer in Hindi grapples with and depicts the rural politics and reality better than Maitreyi Pushpa. The novel *Alma Kabutari* shows the real picture of the woman from primitive race. Alma, the central character makes her appearance fairly late in the novel. She breaks the polite mask of the well-bred society. But she is there in essence all through it. By the character of Alma, Maitreyi Pushpa showed the predicament of such women who belongs to the Kabutari race. She is the quintessence of all that a Kabutari woman stands for. In her abducted condition, Alma forced into becoming a sexual commodity to the kajjas. The kabutara legend has it that Rani Padmini, who is believed to have preferred dying on a burning pyre to falling into the wicked hands of aggressors, actually did not commit 'sati'. She escaped along with a band of guerrilla forces and entered enemy territory eventually co-habituating and producing children whose descendants are the Kabutaras. Alma, the modern-day Padmini, of course without her guerrilla troupe. Being educated she is an oddity in the community. She shares the fate of her illiterate would be mother-in-law and her grandmother. Here is a fate of

repeated sexual exploitation. Rana, her Kabutara lover nurses ambition of becoming a policeman. He becomes Alma's fiancé, only to later desert her. Alma's father is killed by powerful forces to who is serves as a informer. In no time the now-orphaned Alma finds herself in midst of the political machinations of the region. However, she has one advantage that also proves disadvantage many a times. She is not only educated but also has an innate sense of individuality. The man's world ruthlessly uses her as a toy to play with and gain pleasure as well as higher power from. She marries a dacoit-turned-politician and is soon widowed. She uses her newly acquired status to create a power base for herself. The story of Alma's life and therefore the novel is full of dramatic events. The would-be mother-in-law's rapist paramour falls to Kabutara's status himself. Alma's lover becomes insane. All through Alma keeps up her spirits to rise as a phoenix and become a political leader.

Conclusion:

Always the family which is social institution where struggle takes place. Females remain all the time kept into four walls in the earlier days. They fear about the social as well as cultural rules and regulations. Alma becomes the prey of the well-bred society. Pain gives her freedom and time laid out the roads. Wild tracks surrounded by stillness, she threw shame overboard and the modesties and got going or she would have got finished. In this way, women are alienated from Family, Society, Nature and Self.

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